

Efficiency and Effectiveness in Management

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Abstract

This research aims to identify the nature of the relationship between the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness, and shed light on the efforts of Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in achieving efficiency and effectiveness in government agencies and sectors, the researcher concluded that there are two directions regarding the relationship between the two concepts, the first is that effectiveness can be achieved without efficiency and vice versa, and the possibility of the two concepts in the same direction at the same time, and the other that the effectiveness cannot be achieved without efficiency, without the presence of effectiveness, efficiency is not achieved, this is because, according to the definitions presented by "Draker" for both effectiveness and efficiency, it is first important to do the right things (effectiveness) and then do them well (efficiency) second, and he also concluded that the Kingdom was concerned with efficiency and effectiveness in managing government agencies significantly.

The researcher recommended awareness of the relevant parties in institutions about the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness in the administration, and to develop plans and strategies that enhance efficiency and effectiveness within the institution.

Keywords: *Efficiency, Effectiveness, Management.*

INTRODUCTION

Management is an interactive and continuous process, and this process aims to mobilize the collective and individual efforts to achieve the common desired goals, by utilizing the available resources effectively and efficiently (Saudi Knowledge Portal).

Hence, we find that the terms efficiency and effectiveness are related to the concept of public administration, as management is not successful unless there is effectiveness and efficiency in performance.

Efficiency and effectiveness in management are among the important matters in the administrative process. Efficiency in management means doing the right work, i.e. achieving the right goal, and achieving good results for the organization, as for effectiveness, it means completing and supplement work effectively, i.e. achieving

goals (outputs) using the least resources or inputs. . That is, achieving large returns through the use of any available resources or by reducing the resources that are used in the production process (Al-Barzanji and Al-Hawasi, 2014, p. 13).

In the absence of material, financial and informational resources, managers must make use of the resources that are available to them in the best possible way, and successful management must be concerned with achieving both effectiveness and efficiency.

As it is possible to achieve the goals with a high cost, and here we did not achieve effectiveness, but we achieved efficiency only, and it is possible to limit and reduce the cost and use any available resources to us, but we will get a bad result, but we will have achieved effectiveness without efficiency, so good management paying attention to the

concepts of efficiency and effectiveness together.

The interest in efficiency is not a recent matter, but the continuous and regular studies of methods that can contribute to the effectiveness and efficiency of administrative performance, and the emergence of the concept of efficiency in management studies has been accompanied by the emergence of another concept, which is the concept of effectiveness, and that concept has been linked to the concept of efficiency in a strong way to the point of inseparability between the two concepts in most cases, and it has become established in the literature on management that successful things are linked to effectiveness and efficiency, and even most definitions of management and public administration confirm that the goal of administrative activities is to achieve effectiveness and efficiency, but there is also a great confusion between the two concepts in the literature and studies of public administration and management.

Indeed, most of the definitions provided for both "management" and "public administration" confirm that the purpose of any administrative activity is to achieve efficiency and effectiveness. However, there is a great deal of confusion between the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness.

These two concepts were used in mutual ways most of the time, which required further analysis and research of the concepts of effectiveness and efficiency, to accurately distinguish between the two concepts, and also to know the nature of the relationship between them.

Research problem:

With the different types, activities, and objectives of institutions, they are in dire need of resorting to certain criteria, through which one can judge whether those institutions are successful or not, and it is not possible to

use only one criterion to judge whether the institutions are successful or not. Using several criteria to determine the success or failure of institutions, including efficiency and effectiveness, which the researcher will address in this research.

In addition, experts and professors of public administration asserted that the aim of improving, developing and improving administrative activities is to achieve efficiency and effectiveness, but the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness were not defined and what is meant by them specifically, hence, the researcher devoted himself to clarifying the two concepts and knowing the nature of the relationship between them, by dividing the research into the following axes

Axis one: Efficiency.

Axis two: Effectiveness.

Axis three : Efficiency and effectiveness in Saudi government agencies.

Search goal:

This research aims to:

1. Shedding light on the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness.
2. Identify the nature of the relationship between the two concepts.
3. Shedding light on the efforts of Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in achieving efficiency and effectiveness in government agencies and sectors.

Research importance:

The importance of the research is as follows:

1. Encouraging effectiveness and efficiency increases the competitiveness of enterprises.
2. Improving the level of performance of institutions, and activating performance as well.

3. Clarify the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness.

4. Distinguishing between the two concepts, and knowing the nature of the relationship between them.

Previous studies:

When preparing a study or any scientific research, it is necessary to review the previous studies related to the subject of this study or this research, researcher reviewed a lot of literature on the subject of the research, including:

Study by Edwin Rowley and Sybil Sachs Sutter

Towards an Integrated Concept of Management Efficiency.

This study aimed to discuss a number of different criteria and approaches that were used to clarify and evaluate the concept of administrative efficiency, such as (the systems approach, the objective approach, the interactive approach, the social approach, the economic approach, and the decision approach). In this context, the study clarified the difference between the German and American schools in distinguishing between the concepts of effectiveness and efficiency, while the American school differentiates and distinguishes between the two concepts, according to Peter Drucker, who defines efficiency as doing things in the right ways, while effectiveness is doing the right matters and things. German experts and professors such as Friese Grochla and Wilge tended not to distinguish between the terms effectiveness and efficiency.

While the previous study focused on presenting a number of approaches used in defining efficiency, the entitled Kim Cameron's study focused on:

"Effectiveness As Paradox: Consensus and Conflict in Conceptions of Organizational Effectiveness"

On discussing the problems related to the concept of effectiveness, the study emphasized that studies related to the literature of organization suffer from a great deal of confusion between the definition of effectiveness, how to evaluate it, and its distinctive characteristics. The study dealt with three main axes, namely: the points on which the researchers agreed on effectiveness, the points on which they disagreed, and the statement of the contradictory nature of the concept of effectiveness.

CHAPTER ONE: Efficiency

Introduction:

The concept of institutional efficiency represents the rational criterion in the use of available financial, material and human resources and information, institutions that aim at growth and development must ensure the continuity of the material, human and informational flow, in order to achieve its goals effectively and continuously, especially since the reality in contemporary environments is characterized by the scarcity and limitations of available resources, which makes institutions constantly suffer from the difficulty of obtaining those mentioned resources of the qualities and quantities necessary to achieve their goals, and institutions must also not exaggerate in achieving goals with the lack of sufficient necessary resources; This exposes it to severe failure, as it is necessary to achieve compatibility between the desired goals and the available resources (Kharkhash, 2015).

First: The concept of efficiency:

First: Definition of Efficiency in Language:

What is meant by efficiency linguistically: "capability to do a job and to dispose of it

well; ability and good disposal” (Omar, 2008, 942/3). One of the most important definitions of efficiency is the one mentioned by Ibn Mandoor in *Lisan al-Arab*, where he said: “Hassan bin Thabit said: The Holy Spirit has no equivalence. That is, Gabriel, peace be upon him, has no equal” (Ibn Mandoor, 1414 AH, 139/1).

Hence, we conclude that these definitions and meanings revolve around two concepts, namely:

- First: Doing things, and the dictionaries did not specify the level of work , whether they were low or high, nor did specify the percentage of low or high.
- Second: reaching the goal, whether material or moral

Second: Definition of efficiency idiomatically (Farhawi, 2011, p. 11):

-Houston (1979) defines efficiency as: "the ability to produce expected outcomes or bring about expected changes."

- Fisher (1972) points out that efficiency has an economic, engineering and organizational concept, engineering, through the ratio between inputs and outputs, and organizationally, it is the ability of institutions to maintain themselves and the level of satisfaction of the members of those institutions.

- Suhaila Al-Fatlawi (2003) also believes that efficiency in the educational field reflects the extent to which the educational systems are able to achieve the desired goals, while in the teaching field, it is the teachers' knowledge of the importance of each phrase or word he says.

- Efficiency is defined as: work tool in correct ways.

From the above different definitions, we can see that they are all based on ability, which is

difficult to measure, but we can measure some of its effects.

The researcher believes that efficiency expresses the willingness of individuals to employ and integrate the gains they have previously acquired in terms of skills, information and knowledge in adapting to emergency situations and solving emergency problems.

Second: Types of Efficiency:

There are different categories and types of efficiency , including the following:

1.Productive Efficiency: This concept is taken when the largest number of services and goods are created with known quantities of inputs. This relates to the possible limits of production, as it occurs at the lowest point on the average cost curve of the firms. Therefore, it is associated with the production of services and goods with the most beneficial mixture of inputs; To achieve the largest possible amount of production with the lowest amount of costs, it is assumed that the institution will have production efficiency when producing at the lowest point on the average cost curve (marginal costs versus average costs) (Al-Najjar, 2007)

2.Technical efficiency: institutions and organizations must be effective in technical aspects, when they produce the largest production from the smallest amount of determinants, such as technology, labor and capital, and the institution is not technically effective if it uses a large group of employees more than necessary , or capital is employed more than it should be (Ibrahim, 2008).

3. Economic efficiency: It refers to the best use of resources, with the aim of producing the maximum amount of services or goods, and comparison is made between economic systems through the extent of their ability to provide goods and services with the use of fewer resources, and economic efficiency

includes both technical, productivity and price as well (Al Mamari 2010).

4. Allocative efficiency: This is a kind of efficiencies that expresses the situation in which productive institutions reach the best allocation of available resources in front of the relative costs and prices of those resources, and resource allocation expresses the ways in which different resources are distributed to different alternative uses for them. Considering the cost that results from the use of those resources, as the allocative efficiency expresses the production of the best combinations of goods or services through the use of combinations of production elements, and allocative efficiency refers to the following elements: optimal use of input combinations, the best choice of output combinations (Al Mamari, 2010).

5. Fixed or Static Efficiency: This efficiency refers to the most efficient combination of different resources at a specific point in time. Static efficiency includes two parts: the greater production of goods given the goods and services produced in the preferred allocation and the size of the various resources in the economy. This necessarily reflects the technical and technological capabilities preferred by the consumer, For example, static efficiency involves understanding of productive efficiencies, given the different available resources and inputs (Sultan, 2008).

6. Administrative Efficiency: A lot of literature and previous studies dealt with the importance of administrative efficiency and various administrative practices in the success of companies and various government agencies. Administrative efficiency refers to the skills of orientation to tasks related to effective management and leadership, the various administrative practices relate to the use of a methodology or practice that ensures the effective performance of the operations of the institution or the government sector, some say that administrative efficiency depends on

the rate of organizational development, for example, when the company expands, it becomes more complex, so it necessarily needs more advanced practices than before.

From the foregoing, we can say that administrative efficiency express: a set of special knowledge and basic values for the development of the individual's personality, and that they also concern the successful participation of individuals belonging to institutions or government sectors, and in fact express the necessary behavior to achieve the desired level of performance, and this indicates to a side of performance of efficiencies that is determined by measuring the level of inputs (knowledge, behaviors, motivations, attributes, and abilities) that are evaluated through an analysis of outputs (in the form of real behaviors and results).

According to the development of administrative competencies, we can divide it into three main stages:

- First stage: expresses individual efficiency.
- Second stage: The capabilities of managing administrative efficiencies in government institutions and agencies.

Third stage: defining the basic efficiencies, which are all the basic c efficiencies that are related to the organization, through which it is possible to obtain a greater competitiveness.

Many literatures have mentioned the qualities and characteristics of efficiency, such as; decision-making, systems of thinking, and having a desire to learn, also mentioned set of characteristics and traits, such as:

- o Negotiation and communication skills.
- o Systems of thinking, systems orientation of operations.
- o Decision making and analysis skills.
- o To have an initiative personality.

It enables the evaluation and measurement of administrative efficiency to compare with certain job behaviors, and enables us to know if the individual or the process is at the desired level of effectiveness and efficiency, the development and identification of administrative efficiencies brings many advantages to institutions and sectors, and through this it is possible to expand the work capabilities of managers, and thus contributes to the development of the capabilities of the work teams and thus the institution, so it is necessary to have programs that must have clear perceptions that take into account the changes that may occur in the future (Thani, 2017)

Third: Dimensions, Importance, and Characteristics of Efficiency:

Efficiency Dimensions:

When analyzing efficiency deeply and accurately, we find that it is related to both the organizational and individual levels; Where the organizational level coordinates individual efficiency, and when looking at the individual level, we find that studies have multiplied in analyzing and studying how efficiencies are formed, which made the individual level have several dimensions. T. Dunand combined studies and research and concluded that there are three dimensions of efficiencies, which are as follows: The following (Mousavi and Khalidi, 2005, p. 177):

1. Knowledge:

It is a specific set of information that is assimilated, structured and integrated through a clear frame of reference that allows the organization to lead its own activities and work within its own framework, It expresses a necessary set of basic professional knowledge for job practices, such as secretarial techniques and accounting techniques.

2. Technical knowledge skills:

Technical knowledge skills expresses the ability to act in a tangible capacity, keeping in mind pre-established goals.

3. Behavioral and Self-Knowledge:

This kind of knowledge has been neglected for a long time, It is also called relational knowledge, and it is represented in the set of attitudes, behaviors, and personal characteristics that are associated with the employee, and which are required of him when performing certain activities.

The importance of efficiency:

The concept of efficiency occupies a great deal of attention within organizations and agencies at all levels, whether at the individual or the collective level, the level of human resources management, and then at the organizational level, and the following are mentioned in some detail (Bouyahyawi and Bin Ahmed, 2016):

First: The Importance of efficiency at the Individual Level:

Efficiency represent the greatest importance for individuals within organizations; Because there are many new challenges resulting from the recent transformations, which are characterized by great difficulty, and there are several reasons that led to the interest of individuals in efficiency more, namely:

1. Fear of losing work, whether by layoffs or transfers, due to the existence of competitive requirements that are constantly renewed and increasingly difficult.

2. Maximizing the individual's opportunity to obtain a job that matches his level of ambition, when that individual possesses the relevant efficiencies to a large extent.

3. The large number of individuals with university degrees, as this reduces the individuals' ability to obtain a job or work

commensurate with the aspirations they possess.

Second: The importance of efficiency at the collective level:

Efficiency is an important element for the successful functioning of teamwork within the organization, and its importance is shown in the following:

1. Successful business within the organization is based on synergy and cooperation between all individuals, due to the rapid developments in studies, concepts, results, and information society, many new needs have also emerged for the organization, which has led to reliance on efficiencies network systems consisting of individual efficiencies, where each individual contributes to the enrichment and renewal of this network, which facilitates the solution of organizational or production problems.
2. Efficiencies at the collective level contribute to resolving conflicts between members of organizations and agencies without the need to resort to the manager or the authority, which instills within individuals a spirit of team and cooperation, and this is in the interest of the agency or institution.

Third: The importance of efficiency at the level of human resource management:

Efficiencies are a very important factor that managers pay attention to at the level of human resource management efficiencies, as attention shifts from focusing on individual efficiencies to focusing on team efficiency, and the principle of multiple efficiencies instead of specialized efficiencies emerges in all businesses and jobs.

Fourth: The importance of efficiencies at the institutional level:

The strategic vision is based on many things, the most important of which is the process of developing efficiencies, as it is considered in most cases the controlling and defining of all

management operations; Because they represent the most important and largest strategic and basic resources of the organization, and therefore organizations that want to achieve efficiency in overall performance at a high level pay great attention to administrative efficiencies.

Efficiency Characteristics:

The efficiency characteristics are as follows:

1. It has a goal and an end, so the individual is competent if he can perform his work fully.
2. It is formulated in dynamic ways, as all its constituent elements interact with each other in a vicious circle of knowledge and technical knowledge.
3. The concept of efficiency is abstract, it is not visible, it cannot be observed, only used means and administrative activities are observed, and it is determined whether those activities have been efficiently accomplished or not by analyzing their results.
4. It is acquired: the individual is not born with efficiency, but rather the individual acquires it through directed training.
5. A competent individual is characterized by the ability to scientifically evaluate, analyze, and understand quickly (Bouyahyawi and Bin Ahmed, 2016).

CHAPTER TWO: Effectiveness

Introduction:

The institution effectiveness index is one of the important indicators in measuring the extent to which the institution's objectives are achieved, taking into account the environment in which it operates, in terms of the use of the various available resources, the concept of enterprise effectiveness, like other management concepts, has been exposed to a difference in intellectual points of view in terms of defining its precise and comprehensive meaning..

First: the concept of effectiveness:

The literature and studies that dealt with the concept of effectiveness were characterized by not a little chaos, as there are those who define it as: the ability of the institution to achieve profit, and the ability of the organization to increase the number of customers, and the degree of satisfaction of these customers with the provided services to them, and there are those who define it as: achieving satisfaction of working individuals, and there are who define it as: the extent of the institution's ability to provide things that have value to society, and management researchers presented many definitions of the concept of effectiveness, including:

- Peter F. Drucker expressed effectiveness as doing the right things, and then effectiveness measures the ability of the organization to achieve the goals and objectives that were set in advance. Peter Drucker suggested five requirements that must be present to achieve organizational effectiveness, namely: Promote organizational structure, time management, decision making, prioritization and results orientation. (Roghania, Rosli & Gheysaria, 2012)
- Both Bluedorn and Etzioni agree on defining the concept of effectiveness as: the ability of an organization to achieve its predetermined goals and mission. (Roghania, Rosli & Gheysaria, 2012)
- While Ramnaraya and Gaerter point out that effectiveness is not only related to the organization's outputs, but it is a continuous process that links the organization to the surrounding environment, an effective organization is an organization that is able to create acceptable accounts for its activities and for itself, and these accounts can be for multiple purposes and for diverse activities and diverse audiences (Mouzas).
- Dervitsiotis defines the effectiveness of the organization as: the values that the business

creates for the beneficiaries, meaning that the effectiveness focuses on the outputs of the institutions, and among the factors influencing the effectiveness is the way management deals with the beneficiary, customer satisfaction with the service or product, and community participation in development programs and plans (Mohammed, 2015).

- Beckhard also defines an effective organization as one that is characterized by openness, awareness, and the ability of individuals to interact with changes that occur in the surrounding environment (Ibid.).

The researcher believes that effectiveness reflects the ability of the working individual to deal with an urgent and surrounding challenges, and it is the measure that measures the extent to which the goals and plans set by the institutions are achieved.

Second: The relationship between the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness:

As a result of mixing between the concept of effectiveness and efficiency, controversy arose among thinkers of public administration, some of them, including Santiago Simpas, Ramon M. Garcia, argued that effectiveness can be achieved without efficiency and vice versa, and from this we conclude that the two concepts may not work in the same direction at the same time.

While Peter Drucker argued that effectiveness cannot be achieved without efficiency, without effectiveness there is no efficiency, because according to the definitions given by Drucker for both effectiveness and efficiency, it is important first to do the right things (effectiveness) and then do them well (Efficiency) secondly (Mohammed, 2015, p. 15).

Axis Three : Efficiency and effectiveness in Saudi government agencies

The Kingdom has paid great attention to the efficiency and effectiveness in managing government agencies, as the researcher will explain in the following;

First: Efficiency and effectiveness in light of the ninth and tenth development plans:

In support of efforts to raise administrative efficiency in Saudi government agencies, Cabinet Resolution No. (129) dated (2007) was issued to establish an internal audit unit in each of the public institutions and government agencies, It is responsible for evaluating internal control systems, and ensuring the extent to which government agencies comply with financial procedures, regulations, systems, and instructions

The years of the plan also witnessed the restructuring of a number of government agencies and institutions, such as the Saudi Arabian Agricultural Bank, the modification of its name to the Agricultural Development Fund, and the restructuring of some departments related to the Ministry of Electricity and Water and conversed into a joint stock company under the name of the National Water Company.

In the light of the Kingdom's development strategy, the vision focused on effectiveness, and the vision was as follows: "An advanced institutional and administrative structure that ensures the achievement of effectiveness, efficiency and justice in business management and government activities, including planning development projects in general, implementing and evaluating their programs, as well as administrative development and administrative reform in particular, in a manner that leads ultimately, to meet the needs of the beneficiaries of government services and products in a quick and effective manner, within the framework of the state's policies and future directions" (Ministry of Economy and Planning).

Second; A previous study on the issue of efficiency and effectiveness in government sectors:

Zeila's study (2013) entitled: "The role of oversight bodies in raising the efficiency of the performance of government agencies. This study aims to identify the extent of the oversight agencies' satisfaction with the efficiency of the performance of government agencies, as well as the extent of their satisfaction with their oversight role in raising the efficiency of the performance of government agencies, and the most prominent obstacles that hinder them from playing this role, and how the performance of these agencies can be improved to carry out their role in raising the efficiency of performance of government entities, to achieve these goals, the descriptive analytical approach was used by designing a questionnaire consisting of five axes to survey the views of a sample of workers in the control agencies, the sample amounted to (314), in each of the Shura Council, Control and Investigation Authority, the Ministry of Finance, the General Auditing Bureau, and the Shura Council. The study concluded that the majority of regulatory agencies are not satisfied with the efficiency of government agencies' performance for several reasons, the most important of which is the spread of nepotism and the weak effectiveness of implementing public projects. The study also found that the majority of regulatory bodies are somewhat satisfied with their role in raising the efficiency of the performance of government agencies, with some obstacles that impede the performance of these agencies, most notably weak material incentives for auditors, and the lack of guarantees that ensure these agencies work more freely, also put forward a number of scientific and academic recommendations.

Conclusion

Efficiency and effectiveness in management are among the important matters in the

administrative process, efficiency in management means doing the right work, i.e. achieving the right goal, and achieving good and important results for the organization. as for effectiveness, it means doing and completing the work effectively, i.e. achieving goals (outputs) using the least resources or input. That is, achieving significant returns through the use of any available resources or by reducing the resources that are used in the production process.

Efficiency expresses the willingness of individuals to employ and integrate the gains they have previously acquired in terms of skills, information and knowledge in adapting to emergency situations and solving emergency problems.

Effectiveness expresses the ability of the working individual to deal with the urgent and surrounding challenges, and it is the measure that measures the extent to which the goals and plans set by the institutions are achieved.

As a result of mixing the concept of effectiveness and efficiency, controversy arose among public administration thinkers, some of them argued that it is possible to achieve effectiveness without efficiency and vice versa, and from this we conclude that the two concepts may not move in the same direction at the same time.

Others argued that effectiveness cannot be achieved without achieving efficiency, and without effectiveness, efficiency cannot be achieved, because according to the definitions that Drucker gave for both effectiveness and efficiency, it is important first to do the right things (effectiveness) and then do them well (efficiency) secondly. .

The Kingdom paid great attention to the efficiency and effectiveness in managing government agencies, and this appeared through what the researcher mentioned in the third axis.

The researcher recommends educating the relevant parties in institutions about the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness in management, and developing plans and strategies that enhance efficiency and effectiveness within institutions.

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